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Review Article

Prasutitantra And Strirog in Charak Samhita: A Classical Elaboration

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ABSTRACT

Ayurved has explained all types of diseases occurring in human body with its prophylactic, preventive and curative line of treatment by various books called AYURVED SAMHITA. Acharya Charak, Sushrut and Vagbhat are the pioneers of these. Charak Samhita mainly describes the medical faculty diseases occurring by infections and systemic disorders. Sushrut Samhita mainly deals with the surgical part. Ayurved has many faculties that deals with the different systems of body, female reproductive system is one of it. The faculty that describes this system is called PRASUTI TANTRA and STRIROG. Both acharyas have described the medical and surgical part of this body system very minutely. Unfortunately, by the time the manuscripts got destroyed. The remains show rich and sublime thoughts observations and explanation that today's advance science reflects of ancient knowledge. Acharya Charak has described thoroughly this part, by this study I am trying to throw a light on it.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurved is an ancient system of medicine. It is like a guide for a healthy lifestyle. It is a comprehensive health manual with a minute observation of a long span. Each of the information given in Samhita proved its significance by the time. Charak Samhita covered all aspects of medicine by focusing on Diagnosis Treatment and Preventive guidelines. These methods are proved key line in this epidemic too. All aspects of medicine are described in 120 chapters, 9295 sutra and 12000 shlokas. Mainly

sutrasthan, sharirsthan, chikitsasthan included all the information about Prasutitantra and strirog. Garbhadhan means with all health measures formation of new life [fetus] till death of a human. Anatomy and Physiology of human body. Function and malfunction of system with Tridosh, Pancha Mahabhut, Strotus, Dhatu with its Dhatwagni. Knowledge of Diseases Diagnosis and its treatment by Herbal Medicines, Raskalp, Rasayan, vajikaran, panchakarma chikitsa padhati. The prevention and curative methods like yoga and meditation with medicine for psychological

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aspect of life, Physiotherapy, diet, logical and Philosophical Guidance.

Prasutitantra and strirog described in it mainly deals with Aartavaha strotus from Menarche to Menopause, Garbhadhan to sutikavastha the total life cycle of a female. By the time and circumstances what remained till date also gives the trailer of developed perspective of our acharya and defines the approach or outlook in present scenario for development and research in subject.

A. Sutrasthan:

chapter 4: shadvirechanashritiya, described about garbhsthapak gan [1] for proper fetal development, prajasthan gan to avoid abortion bleeding during pregnancy, Garbhvyapad the diseases occurring to foetus.

chapter19: Ashtodariya, described Ashtakshirdosh [2] diseases of breast milk with its treatment.

chapter30: Arthedashmahamuliya...described yonivyapad diseases of reproductive system [3], Vinshati yonivyapad diseases of trayaverta yoni [uterus, cervix and vagina]

kumarbharan koumarbhrutya varnan [4].

Menstrual disorders like metrorrhagia, dysmenorrhea, menorrhagia

Asrugdar Pradara Yonigat raktastrav the bleeding from uterus [5] related to dysfunctional uterine bleeding with its treatment.

Raktagulm cyst and fibroids [6] abnormal growth in or to the wall of uterus or ovaries.

Infertility with its treatment, Transgender Shandi yoni specially Napunsaktwa is described in Charaksamhita [7].

B. Sharirsthan:

Chapter 2: Shukra and shonit varnan [8] Ovum and sperm norma lstructure Impact of maternal and paternal factors called matruj pitruj bhav according to modern science the genetic influence on fetus. [9]

Gender formation according to chromosomal formulation [10].

Chapter 3: formation of zygote the fertilized ovum by fusion of sperm [shukra] and ovum [streebeej /shonit] [11] process of fertilization responsible factors.

Chapter 4: Garbhdharana kal, ovulation period [rutumati].

Garbhadhan Fertilization [12]

Panch bhoutiktra [13] The organ formation of fetus by panchmahabhut Prithvi, Aakash, Agni, Jal, Vaayu and its tanmatra [criteria of function] the effects or functioning like sound by vayu, tej by agni etc.

Trigun... Satwa, Raj, Tam responsible for formation and functions of systems of body and respective organs the characters are decided by this. Conception [Garbh sthapana] the pregnancy and factors responsible for growth of fetus [Garbh vridhikar bhav] [14].

Garbh sthapak gan [15] The medicines helping for proper growth of fetus in womb to avoid abortion [Miscarriage].

Chapter 8: Garbhini Paricharya the Antenatal care,

Garbhsanskar for a healthy progeny and Putreshti yadnya for a bestowed pregnancy.

Punsavn nasya chikitsa the nasal infiltration of oil or some drug extracts for a healthy baby [16]

Position of fetus in uterus called garbhsthati [17]

Abortion according to gestational period [Garbhstrav and Garbhpaat /Ajatsar garbh] with treatment. [18]

Presentation of fetal occiput at nine month of gestational period Awakshirsa Avastha the vertex presentation [19]

uterine contractions/labour pains at term [20]

prelabour care like basti medicated enema, oil pichu the tampons to smoothen vaginal and perineal muscles for a smooth labour process [21].

Prasavkaal [22] Negle's rule time of labour... expulsion of foetus at term.

IUD/ STILLBIRTH mrutgarbh varnan[23]called Garbhini vyapad.

Achesht balak paricharya according to APGAR score if the newborn needs resuscitation that is well described in Charak Samhita [24].

postnatal care of mother n newborn Sutika pricharya till restoration of ovulation. Sutikagaar varnan[25]

C. Sidhistan

Chapter 12: Infertility treatment [sneh and niruh basti] medicated enema with oil and decoction.[26]

D. Chikitsa sthan

Chapter 30: Gynaecological disorders yonivyapad varnan Diseases of Reproductive System their reasons with treatment [27].

DISCUSSION

Aacharya Charak explained all the phages of life like cycle birth till death with its essential's difficulties and solution and the preventive methods.

Garbhadhan prakriya fertilization to fetal full growth till labour. Normal conception needed factors, the abnormalities in eproductive system; sribeej ovum, shukra sperm formation expulsion and fusion, their abnormalities the line of treatment is exclusively disessed. Napunsakata, shandi, yoni, varnan, rasayan, vajikaran, chikitsa in detail he described. Garbhini paricharya the antenatal care, garbhini lakshana care of mother n fetus in womb he described well. Mrutgarbha, garbhstraav and paat, abortion IUD, stillbirth, resuscitation of newborn is also expressed well. Diseases of genital tract male n female are included with different line of treatments. Causes, pathology, sign and symptoms with treatment preventive and absolute line of treatment in infertility is described. Breast changes in pregnancy, breast milk disorders with line of treatment are described.

Manovikar, rajnivrutti, rasayan, chikitsa, are also point to be taken in consideration for discussion in this era.

CONCLUSION

Charak Samhita is full guide for a better life, a bestowed pregnancy. A best guide manual for herbal remedies no side effects, to avoid hazards or complications during lifetime with a proper lifestyle, preventive and curative line of treatment.

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